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A RETROSPECTIVE OF THE IMPACT OF THE PANDEMIC ON GLOBALIZATION

Gabriela Radetić <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4171-3691>¹

Summary:

Research question (RV): What does the crisis (Covid-19) mean for globalization?

Purpose: Looking at the global crisis affected by Covid-19 and the Russia-Ukraine war.

Method: The author used general scientific methods in his work - hypothetical deductive method.

Results: It can be argued that the coronavirus has not only affected our lives, but, it seems, has fundamentally changed them. Although it affected numerous factors, primarily the economy, health, and many others, it seems that the society is slowly returning to normal, although it will take a long time. However, the bigger problem seems to be whether we have learned from it all.

Limitations/further research: How much will the current war between Russia and Ukraine disrupt the post-pandemic recovery?

Keywords: recession; global economy; travel industry; work from home; geopolitical tensions.

RETROSPEKTIVNI PREGLED VPLIVA PANDEMIJE NA GLOBALIZACIJO

Povzetek:

Raziskovalno vprašanje (RV): Kaj pomeni kriza (Covid-19) za globalizacijo?

Namen: Preučitev globalne krize, na katero sta vplivali Covid-19 in rusko-ukrajinska vojna.

Metoda: Avtor je pri svojem delu uporabil splošne znanstvene metode - hipotetično deduktivno metodo.

Rezultati: Lahko trdimo, da koronavirus ni le vplival na naša življenja, ampak jih je, kot kaže, tudi temeljito spremenil. Čeprav je vplival na številne dejavnike, predvsem na gospodarstvo, zdravje in številne druge, se zdi, da se družba počasi normalizira, čeprav bo za to potrebno še veliko časa. Vendar se zdi, da je večji problem, ali smo se iz vsega tega kaj naučili.

Omejitve/nadaljnje raziskave: Koliko bo sedanja vojna med Rusijo in Ukrajino ovirala okrevanje po pandemiji?

Ključne besede: recesija, svetovno gospodarstvo, potovalna industrija, geopolitične napetosti

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Introduction

Globalization has been one of the predominant words in the last 25 years. It may seem like a rather unusual concept, since any economic historian will assert that people have traded over vast distances for centuries, if not millennia. To know this, one should only consider the medieval spice trade or the East India Company. But the essence of globalization bears a resemblance to the scale and speed of international business, which have exploded in the last few decades to inviolable heights. Easier travel, the Internet, the end of the Cold War, trade agreements and, most recently, rapid economic growth, together make up a system that depends much more on what is happening on the other side of the world than ever before.

The coronavirus pandemic has affected almost every country in the world. The whole world was shaken by the virus epidemic which broke out in Wuhan, China, since the supply of Chinese products stopped. Meanwhile, the virus has spread around the world. Although production is slowly restarting both in Europe and in other parts of the world, it is still creaking throughout the system. In many ports, only a part of the staff has been hired due to the corona virus, and new regulations make logistics more difficult. European shipping companies, for example, continue to reduce capacity by half, to match supply and demand.

Research results

In modern European-style capitalism, the economic principle takes precedence over the political. The interests of firms and the labor market are determined by national policies. The COVID-19 epidemic has changed that hierarchy, because for almost a year now, politics has been controlling the economy worldwide. The whole world is facing problems at the moment. The developed countries are able to withstand these closures for a longer period of time, contrary to the underdeveloped countries. The difference being in the fact that developed countries can borrow on much more favorable terms. The spread of the virus has left national economies and businesses counting the costs, as governments struggle with new lockdown measures to tackle the spread of the virus. Despite the development of new vaccines, many are still wondering what recovery could look like.

The IMF states that the economic downturn is the worst since the Great Depression of the 1930s. According to them, the pandemic took the world into a "crisis that did not exist". If the pandemic lasts long, it will test the ability of governments and central banks to control the crisis, they added. Although the IMF praised the "quick reaction" in countries such as Great Britain, Germany, Japan and the United States, it is stated that no country will be immune to economic decline. A partial recovery is projected for 2021, "Gopinath says. "But the level of gross domestic product will remain below the level it was before the virus outbreak, with uncertainty as to how much it will be able to recover." The IMF warns that growth in developed economies will not return to pre-virus levels until 2023.

The American economy recorded a decline of 5, 9 % in 2020, which is the largest annual decline since 1946. At the same time, unemployment is expected to jump to 10, 4 %.

Figure 1: Yearly unemployment rate change, 2019 and 2020 compared

In the United States, the proportion of unemployed people reached a yearly total of 8.9%, according to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), signalling an end to a decade of jobs expansion.

<https://www.bbc.com/news/business-51706225>

Millions of workers have also been put on government-supported job retention schemes within the economy. Moreover, tourism and hospitality industries have come to a near standstill. New job opportunities are still very scarce in many countries. Job vacancies in Australia have dropped to the same level as they were in 2019, but they are lagging in France, Spain, the UK and several other countries. Some experts have warned it could be years before levels of employment return to those before the pandemic.

Figure 2: Daily percentage change in the number of job postings 2020 and 2019 (<https://www.bbc.com/news/business-51706225>)

The pandemic prevents cross border workers from South East Europe to EU countries

A major disruption to the usual flow of labor was felt throughout Southeastern Europe - the source of millions of foreign workers moving from East to West year by year. The loss of employment opportunities threatens the already poor standard of living in Ukraine and the Western Balkans - Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Northern Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia - which have been regular exporters of labor to Western Europe for decades. However, this problem also creates issues and concerns among EU member states in Central and Southeast Europe - Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, Poland and Romania.

Some of these countries are both importers and exporters of workers. They rely on cheaper labor from Ukraine or the Balkans to fill lower-skilled jobs, often to replace their own citizens, who were looking for more lucrative jobs in the Western Europe - mainly Germany, the UK or the Netherlands. The pandemic hit foreign workers in the EU the hardest, as they were among the first to lose their jobs or have their salaries reduced. This, in turn, affects living standards throughout Southeast Europe. So far, the coronavirus pandemic has had the least impact on more developed countries which are less dependent on the labor force, such as the Czech Republic and Hungary. However, that could change if the pandemic continues to spread uncontrollably during 2022. Despite this, analysts expect the number of migrant workers, including those from the Western Balkans, to decline if the COVID-19 crisis continues. The risk of economic slowdown and unemployment is obvious, even if conditions remain stable in the meantime. The infection will repel migrant workers travelling to the country, further harming the tourism industry and delaying economic recovery. Jobs in the hospitality industry are especially exposed, as well as tourism, which is still on its knees.

The situation with the coronavirus is causing big problems in the automotive industry, which is forced to stop or limit work in factories. All spheres of logistics are largely affected by the pandemic, but to a different extent. The automotive industry has lost almost 100 % of its turnover. Also, in the fields of electronics, machine and textile industries, the demand has almost completely dropped. In contrast to the mentioned branches, the demand in the pharmacological and food industry has clearly increased, though partly disproportionately. Professor Beata Javorcik, chief economist at the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, states that the change in the global economy over the past 17 years has left a deep mark. "Looking back on 2003 and the Sars epidemic, China then accounted for 4 % of global production," she states. "China now makes four times as much, 16 %. That means that whatever happens in China today has an impact on the whole world to a much greater extent."

The notion of globalization can easily clarify why almost every major car factory in the UK has stopped its production - they depend on sales and components from all parts of the world. When they both dried up, they just stopped making cars.

China's wealth and health, therefore, are much more important to us than they once were, but it is not just a question of scale - globalization implies a much deeper problem.

Figure 3: Majority of countries in recession, Real GDP growth

The only major growing economy in 2020 was China. It registered a growth of 2,3%.

The IMF is, however, predicting global growth of 5,2% in 2021. That will be driven primarily by countries such as India and China, forecast to growth by 8,8% and 8,2% respectively. Recovery in big, services-reliant, economies that have been hit hard by the outbreak, such as the UK or Italy, is expected to be slow.

<https://www.bbc.com/news/business-51706225>

Ian Goldin, a professor and expert of globalization and development at Oxford University as well as author of *The Butterfly Effect: How Globalization Creates Systemic Risks and What to Do About It*, says that "risks are allowed to fester, they have become a chronic state of globalization." That, he states, can be seen not only now, but also in the credit crunch and banking crisis of 2008 and the vulnerability of the Internet to cyber-attacks. The new global economic system brings enormous benefits, but also enormous risks. Although it has helped to increase earnings, to rapidly develop the economies of countries and lift millions of people out of poverty, it has also brought upon extremely high risk of deterioration, both financial or health.

What does this latest crisis mean for globalization? For example, in the store - when supply chains were interrupted due to the corona virus, people started looking for alternative suppliers at home, even if they were more expensive. When people find domestic suppliers, they will continue to collaborate with them... because of these identified risks.

Professor Javorcik believes that the combination of these factors will suggest that the Western factory industry will start returning work home or doing "reshoring", as it is professionally called. "I think the trade war (mostly between the United States and China), combined with the corona virus epidemic, will lead companies to take reshoring seriously," she said. "They will reschedule activities that can be automated, because resorption brings certainty. You don't have to worry about your national trade policy, and it gives you the opportunity to diversify your supply base." However, this is not just beneficiary for Western economies, which will now probably think they have become too dependent on globalization. Instead, it works in both directions.

The fundamental nature of globalization is not transporting manufactured goods around the world, but also in transporting people, ideas and information; which is something the UK and other Western economies are very good at. As David Henning, director of British trade policy at the European Center for International Political Economy, points out: "The service sector must have suffered a major blow, just look at tourism and universities in particular." "There must be great concern about the number of new enrollments at Western universities. It's a huge export industry, many universities depend on Chinese students, for example." Many Western universities will lack foreign students who often have to pay more for their studies and make up a key revenue stream.

The notion that the fundamental nature of globalization is in moving production or supply chains to cheaper Asian countries is too simplistic. It has also led to a massive increase in the number of foreign students willing to pay to study at our colleges and universities and a huge influx of wealthy tourists who want to spend money here, to name just two businesses in the service sector. Slowing down or reversing globalization will really hit these branches hard. As David Henning, director of British trade policy at the European Center for International Political Economy, points out: "The service sector must have suffered a major blow, just look at tourism and universities in particular." Although some of these factors are already being felt, such as 3D printing, automation, the demand for adaptation to specific needs and fast delivery, just like protectionism, it seems that Covid-19 can only speed up the process. The essence of much of globalization is not in transporting manufactured goods around the world, but also in transporting people, ideas and information.

Figure 4: Industries damaged by Covid-19 are key investment vehicles (share of global cross border M&A and greenfield FDI projects, 2019, % by value)

Overall, the UN’s trade and development body (UNCTAD) expects the pandemic to reduce global FDI flows by about 40% in 2020-21, a slightly deeper contraction than the 35% recorded during the global financial crisis in 2008-09. However, the actual impact could be more dramatic given the greater breadth, depth and complexity of the current situation. *

The real question, however, is not whether these changes will happen, but how far-reaching they will be and how they will be resolved? Will the result resemble the period after the First or the Second World War? We could, as after 1918, witness wearing of international organizations, a rise in nationalism, protectionism and economic crisis. Or, as after 1945, more cooperation and internationalization, such as Bretton Woods, the Marshall Plan, the UN and the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade.

"We can be optimistic, but we certainly don't see leadership coming from the White House," David Henig pointed out. "China can't take the reins, and Britain can't lead Europe." Professor Jonathan Portes shares this concern, emphasizing: "The London G20 summit in 2009 agreed on a package of international cooperation worth one trillion dollars, and even Germany joined it." But now there is no leadership in the G20, and the United States is absent from the international scene. "

Where will we be in six months, in a year or ten years from now? I lie awake at night and wonder what kind of future awaits the people I love. My fragile friends and relatives. There are several possible futures, depending on how governments and society will deal with the coronavirus and its consequences for the economy.

We hope to use the crisis to rebuild society, create something better and more humane. But we could also sink into something worse. I think we can assess at our situation - as well as what lies ahead - by looking at other crises. My research focuses on the fundamentals of the modern economy: the global supply chain, earnings, and productivity.

* <https://www.eiu.com/n/campaigns/down-but-not-out-globalisation-and-the-threat-of-covid-19/>

I analyze at how economic developments affect challenges such as climate change and the poor mental and physical health of workers. Isolation puts pressure on the global economy. We are facing a great recession. This pressure has led some world leaders to suggest easing isolation measures. The economy of collapse is quite simple. Entrepreneurs strive to make a profit. If they don't produce anything, they have nothing to sell. This means that they will not make a profit, which means that they will be less and less able to hire staff. Entrepreneurs can (for a short period of time) keep workers they do not need directly - and they do: they want to be able to meet market demands when the economy recovers. But if things get really bad, they won't do it. As a result, more and more people are losing their jobs or fearing dismissal. And then they buy less and less. Thus, the whole cycle starts from the beginning and takes us through the whirlpool of economic depression.

In the usual crisis, the recipe for solving this process is simple - the government spends money, until people start consuming and working again. Currently, the basic goal of the global economy is to ensure the exchange of money. Economists call it "exchange value". The prevailing idea of the system in which we currently live is that "exchange value" is the same as "use value". Basically, people will spend money on what they want or need, and that act of spending money reveals a lot about how much they value its "usability". Therefore, the market is considered the best way to manage a company. It allows you to adapt and is flexible enough to match production capacity with use value. What Covid-19 clearly shows is the extent to which we misunderstood the market. Around the world, governments fear that the essential systems will collapse or overload: supply chains, social assistance, but mostly health care. There are many factors that contribute to this. First of all, it is quite difficult to make money in many of the most important social activities. This is partly because the most profitable asset is labor productivity growth: to produce more with fewer people. Staff is a big expense, especially those that rely on personal interactions, such as health care. Consequently, productivity growth in the health care sector is usually lower than in other economic activities, so its cost growth is faster than average. Which is more important - people or the economy?

Secondly, jobs in many key industries are not among the most valued in society. Many of the highest paid jobs exist only to provide an exchange: to make a profit. However, since they make a lot of money, we have a lot of advisors, a huge advertising industry and an even bigger financial sector. At the same time, we are facing a crisis of health care and social assistance, so many are often forced to leave the useful jobs they like to do because they do not bring them enough income to live on.

Pointless jobs

Partly precisely because such a large number of people do meaningless work, our response to Covid-19 was not adequate. The pandemic indicates that many jobs are not crucial, while, on the other hand, we lack the necessary workers to react when things go wrong. People are forced to do meaningless jobs because in a society where exchange value is the main principle of the economy, basic necessities of life are mostly available through the market. This means that you have to buy them, and in order to buy them, you need income, which you earn through work.

The other side of this coin is that the most drastic (and most successful) responses to the expansion of Covid-19 that we see call into question market dominance and exchange value. Governments around the world are taking measures that seemed unthinkable three months ago. In Spain, private hospitals have been nationalized. In the United Kingdom, the chances that various forms of transport will be nationalized have become quite high. And France has announced that it is ready to nationalize large companies.

We are also witnessing the collapse of the labor market. Countries such as Denmark and the United Kingdom provide income to people to prevent them from going to work. This is key to implementing successful isolation. These measures are far from perfect. Still, they represent a departure from the principle that people have to work to make money and move towards the idea that people deserve to live even if they are unable to work. This reverses the dominant trends of the last 40 years. In that period, the market and exchange values were seen as the best way to manage the economy. As a result, public systems are under increasing pressure to become part of the market, to be managed as if they were companies that have to make a profit.

In the same way, workers are increasingly exposed to the market – zero-hour employment contracts and part-time economies have removed the layer of protection that once provided stable long-term employment from market fluctuations. Covid-19 seems to be reversing that trend by separating the health care system and labor products from the market and leaving them at the disposal of the state. States produce for many reasons. Some are good, some are bad. But unlike markets, they do not have to produce solely because of exchange value. For forty years, there was a broad economic consensus. This limited the ability of politicians and their advisers to notice shortcomings in the system or imagine alternatives. Such thinking is based on two related beliefs:

- The market provides a quality life, and must be protected
- The market will always return to normal after short periods of crisis

These views are common in many Western countries. But they are strongest in the United Kingdom and the United States, and both countries have proved ill-prepared to fight Covid-19. In the United Kingdom, participants in a private-sector event reportedly summed up Covid-19's approach to the prime minister's senior adviser as follows: "developing herd immunity, protecting the economy, and if some retirees die, then so be it? "The government has denied this, but we would not be surprised if it is true.

The Global tourism industry is crumbling

The travel industry has been badly affected, with airlines cutting flights and customers cancelling business trips and holidays. Due to numerous border closures and visa restrictions, the number of flights is rapidly declining. Globally, between 80 and 90 % of flights are canceled, and most passenger planes are grounded. This is beneficiary for the environment, because aviation alone is responsible for about 2% of global greenhouse gas emissions. As a result of the suspension of air flights (but also other economic activities, especially industrial ones), NASA noticed an impressive reduction in the level of air pollution in the Chinese city of Wuhan, in the midst of the crisis.

Data from the flight tracking service Flight Radar 24 shows that the number of flights globally took a huge hit in 2020 and it is still a long way from recovery.

Figure 5: Total daily commercial flights with seven-day average (<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/its-just-humanscovid-19-puts-global-economy-ventilator-teli>)

Tourism is overrun. They are the first to be run over and the last to rise. A difficult situation awaits countries that rely heavily on tourism and are unable to make short-term alternatives and quickly turn to other areas of the economy. Income will certainly be lower, and there is also the problem of financially preserving the health of travel agencies, hotels, the banking system, or everything related to tourism, as well as the employment of seasonal workers. The question is, is this the end of mass tourism?

The health crisis related to the COVID-19 virus already has very visible consequences on the tourism industry. Photos from around the world have shown us how popular places, which have usually been victims of mass tourism - Venice, Rome, Madrid, look completely devastated, empty. "These photos are disturbing, like frozen images from disaster movies or the apocalypse," writes the Travel Review. And although everyone knows that at some point people will return to the streets, and return to travel, Covid-19 already looks like a "death penalty" for mass tourism.

Thierry Breton, the European Commissioner for the Single Market and Digital Agenda, admitted even before the complete quarantine was declared in most countries, that the tourism industry would suffer "a financial loss of around one billion euros a month" in Europe. The Oxford Institute of Economics estimates that tourism could have an impact "six times greater than that caused by 9/11", with "4.6 million fewer jobs" due to travel cancellations.

Assuming economic activities return to normal in the next few months, how long will it take for tourists to return to their precious habits? Can everything really go back to the way it was before, as if nothing had happened? And as if the virus is gone?

After the start of the pandemic, a large number of people were delight to hear that many museums are moving into the digital age and offering virtual tours. Fifteen of the world's largest museums, for example, have decided to stay (at least partially) "open" online, including the Louvre in Paris, the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam and the Matt in New York. Not to mention the Google Arts and Culture Platform, which since 2011 has offered virtual visits to specific museums or places, as well as the ability to view thousands of works in high resolution.

Is this enough to distract people from traveling? And especially from mass tourism? What defines tourism is mobility, freedom of movement and confidence in security. And for now, it is impossible to say when all countries will lift the travel ban, open the borders and allow foreign citizens to enter. However, the desire to travel is huge and one can expect mass tourism to easily recover from the current crisis. At least in those most popular tourist destination.

Billions of dollars have been lost in 2020 and although the forecast for 2021 was better, there was very little movements. Many analysts believe that international travel and tourism won't return to the normal pre-pandemic levels until around 2025.

Figure 6: Weekly percentage change in the number of reservations 2019 v 2020 (<https://www.bbc.com/news/business-51706225>)

Source: ShopperTrak, 24 January 2021, 00:01 GMT

Figure 7: Huge drop in shoppers Annual percentage change of footfall 12-28 Jan 2021 compared to same dates 2020

Separate research suggests that consumers are still feeling anxious about their return to stores. Accountancy giant EY says 67% customers are now not willing to travel more than 5 kilometers for shopping. This change in shopping behavior has significantly boosted online retail, with a global revenue of \$3.9 trillion in 2020. The pandemic has transformed the entire shopping experience of a customer at each stage of the purchase journey – pre purchase, during purchase and post purchase.

The pre-purchase consideration stages have elongated as the consumer now factors in much more thought before the actual purchase. While groceries and non-prescriptive medicine category will have strong growth with customers already shopping for such products and increasing spends from pre-pandemic levels, apparels, accessories and furniture stores will experience a longer-term recovery with customers delaying purchases till after the pandemic. Customers are also wary of travelling long distances to shop at their preferred locations, with 67% customers not willing to travel more than 5kms for shopping. Retailers will need to optimize their store layout and adopt practices that reduce crowding and enable customers to shop quickly. Going shopping is no less than going on a mission during the pandemic with 68% customers preferring to wear protective gear and 60% customers making shopping lists to reduce time spent in store.

The traditional brick and mortar channel of retail has been under siege by online/omni channel platforms ever since mobile technology evolved. With the onset of Covid-19, there is an increasing thrust on retailers to readjust their business operations to account for increasing preference for online and contactless purchases and decreasing preference for visiting stores physically. Given that majority of the customers are neither willing to enter the store nor willing to spend more than 30 minutes inside the store, the entire in-store shopping experience that might have therapeutic for some people is instead causing anxiety.

Work from home, good or bad?

Is this the road to lasting change?

Covid-19 could permanently change the way people work, as companies forced to allow remote work due to the pandemic may confront employees who will not want to return to offices when the restrictions are lifted, writes The Guardian. The sudden increase in work from home brings problems as well as opportunities, estimates the British paper. On the one hand, some technology companies

are now offering their software tools for free in the hope that people who use them in times of crisis will continue to use them when it is over. On the other hand, some systems are already on the verge of bursting. For example, corporate networks that are not designed for most connections to go over virtual private networks (VPNs) show unusual interference.

However, it seems that the situation will not return to the old way, the Guardian points out that many workers who were sent by companies to work from home are already wondering why they had to go to offices at all. Large technology companies, such as Amazon, LinkedIn, Microsoft, Google and Twitter, were the first to turn to telecommuting, relying on existing infrastructure but also relying on the fact that most business knowledge-based can be done remotely, as the paper points on. WordPress director Matt Mullenweg says millions will have the opportunity to experience days without long public transport rides or rigid rules that they can't stay home when a family member is ill. "This could be a chance for a big reset in terms of how we work," he stated. Regardless of technology, there comes a time when even introverts want to see another human being.

Video conferencing, a new way of communication

Millions of employees and students who are required to work and learn from home are discovering one of the craziest aspects of modern technology - video conferencing software. In the comfort of their homes - from couches, armchairs, beds and kitchen tables - people around the world, because of the corona virus, use video chats and conferences instead of meetings and classes, social distancing measures that should protect health from contact with other people, create the need for virtual connectivity.

The reality of video conferencing, however, according to the Washington Post, is a mixture of confusing software, bad hardware and the discomfort of social norms that are still in their infancy. For people pushed into the life of working from home for the first time, learning video conference behavior can be as tedious as learning how to engage in such a virtual meeting.

The growing use of video conferencing is evidenced by the fact that the company Zoom, which makes the video conferencing program, had the third most popular application in the Apple Store in 2020, and its actions, as the Washington Post points out, reached record values. With millions of people working and learning from home due to the spread of the corona virus, the Internet will be tested due to one of the biggest changes in human behavior, according to The New York Times.

That mass change will strain the internet infrastructure in two ways, the paper points out. First home networks that people have set up in their homes, but also the services of internet providers. The general infrastructure is adapted to have a maximum load in certain parts of the day - when people return from work and connect to the Internet at home.

Large data transmission for work and distance learning will set new maximum Internet traffic values, while many will use the same Internet connections throughout the day with programs that require large amounts of data, which, according to the New York Times, was mostly reserved for offices and schools. ISPs for companies and schools have special packages with the possibility of higher data flow, and on the other hand home networks can be less reliable. Many people have much less capacity than in the workplace and when more people connect to one Wi-Fi network for video conferencing and streaming movies, it can cause downtime and slowdowns.

The use of programs with large amounts of transferred data and online games has already jumped in places where the corona virus has spread, underlines the New York Times, stating that in Italy, young people who were playing computer games increased Internet traffic over one of the networks by more than 90%. Also in Europe, traffic through Cisco's video conferencing programs jumped 80 %.

In a recent Startit Twitter poll, approximately two-thirds of people said they wanted flexibility in the workplace, meaning they had the option of replacing the office with a home armchair as needed. Now, among online surveyed readers, 55,7% are those who would like to choose where to work from. The average grade of general experience with working outside the office is quite high 4,05 which is another confirmation that people want flexibility from their employers. It is interesting that only every ninth respondent (11,7%) does not want to continue working outside the office after the pandemic.

Figure 8: Startit Twitter poll

Since millions of people now work from home, it may be difficult to return to a normal office life.

The rise of pharmaceutical companies

Governments around the world have pledged billions of dollars for a Covid-19 vaccine and treatment options. Shares in some pharmaceutical companies involved in vaccine development have shot up. Moderna, Novavax and AstraZeneca have seen significant rises. But Pfizer has seen its share price fall. The partnership with BioNTech, the high cost of production and management of the vaccine, and the growing number of same-size competitors have reduced the investors' trust in the company to have bigger revenue in 2021.

Figure 9: Percentage change in share value

A number of pharmaceutical companies have started distributing the first doses of the vaccine and many countries have started their vaccination programs. Many more - such as Johnson & Johnson and Sanofi/GSK – have joined the vaccine distribution during 2021. The global output will return to pre-pandemic levels by the end of 2022 after experiencing a sharp decline of 4,2% in 2020, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) said in its economic outlook. The 37-member OECD projects global GDP to rise by around 4.2% in 2021 and by a further 3,7% in 2022, helped by COVID-19 vaccine rollouts and accommodative fiscal and monetary policies.

In the new year, when it comes to the economy, despite the pandemic, the most reasons for optimization are in China. Thanks to the quick reaction and stopping the spread of the epidemic within the country, the People's Republic of China will achieve significantly higher economic growth in the post-corona period than other highly industrialized countries, which will serve as a new impetus and enable it to overtake the United States. The Chinese government has suffered widespread criticism from the West for its nonchalant treatment of the first cases of coronavirus in Wuhan and the warnings of local medical workers, and then for taking too strict measures that did not take basic human freedoms and rights into account when it started the epidemic, such as the right to freedom of movement.

However, the "locking" of Wuhan proved to be very effective, so that several thousand victims and tens of thousands of infected people succeeded, and China was the first to normalize the lives of citizens and economic activities. And not only that - thanks to the early containment of the epidemic in their own country, the Chinese were able to provide assistance in medical equipment and the importance of many countries around the world and thus expand their "soft" influence in the world.

On the other hand, Western industrialized countries, starting with Italy, through Great Britain, especially the United States, due to inefficient response to the infection, have reached the brink of health system collapse and have been forced repeatedly or in the long run and in a wider area of suspension. many economic activities.

In times of economic fear, Europeans could recognize that nationalism is not economically viable. Sweden has chosen its path in the pandemic, but is now facing the same economic difficulties as the rest of Europe. Sweden is really a classic example of the fact that whatever decisions are made by one government, what will happen to its economy also depends on the decisions of the governments of other countries. Sweden has decided not to stop the economy, hoping to limit the economic costs of the crisis so significantly. They do not close, but they close others. As a result, trucks, which are produced in Volvo's factories in Sweden, could not be produced because parts imported from other parts of Europe or the world could not arrive. In the end, they found themselves in a situation where the economic decline in Sweden in 2020 was greater than in some countries like Poland or Austria, which have completely suspended their economies.

In 2020 the world economy was on track to plunge into its worst recession since the Second World War as the coronavirus forced half the world's population to remain indoors, virtually shutting global businesses, trade and travel. Any hopes of a quick recovery were dashed by subsequent waves of the virus, which has killed about 1,5 million people.

Figure 10: GDP growth in percent

At the end of 2020, the British Center for Economic and Business Research (CEBR) went public with the assessment that thanks to good intervention against Covid-19, China will achieve significantly higher economic growth in the coming years than the most developed western countries. (GDP) expressed in dollars as early as 2028, five years earlier than previously predicted.

“China has been very successful in containing the pandemic and that has played a very important role in bringing back activity much more quickly,” says Gita Gopinath, IMF Economic Counselor and Director, Research Department. “There’s been effective policy support provided both in terms of fiscal policy and monetary policy, and China’s exports have also gone up in this environment. And indeed, it is one of those economies that’s returning to the prepandemic projected level in the fourth quarter of 2020, well ahead of other major economies.” On the other hand, the United States, currently the world’s largest economy, experienced a real national catastrophe, about 21 million infected and about 360,000 victims. Although, thanks to huge fiscal stimuli, the American economy has kept its head afloat, British economists believe that in the United States, as a result of the epidemic, over 14 million citizens lost their jobs. According to them, in the period from 2022 to 2024, the American economy should grow at a rate of 1.9%, after which there would be a slight slowdown and an average growth of about 1.6% in the second half of this decade.

On the other hand, they believe that the Chinese economy will achieve an average growth of about 5.7% in the three years after the epidemic has been contained and then continue to grow at a rate of about 4.5% until the end of the decade, already mentioned, it surpasses the United States in the size of its economy already in this decade.

Also, according to CEBR estimates, by the end of this decade, India should, thanks to economic growth that will be higher than China’s, overtake Great Britain, Germany and Japan and become the third largest economy in the world, behind China and the United States. The IMF warns that there are “serious risks of even worse outcomes.” If it takes more time for the pandemic to curb and if there is another wave in 2022-2023, the world’s gross domestic product will fall by another eight percent. The IMF states that this scenario could be a big problem for economies with large debt, because investors will not want to borrow money, which will increase the cost of borrowing. Although quarantine reduces economic activity, the IMF states that it and social distancing are vital measures.

If the world is really moving in the direction of protectionism, if globalization is accompanied by regionalization and a certain amount of deglobalization: most European countries, even the largest ones such as France and Germany, are too small to be economically protectionist. Similarly to Europe and the rest of the world, a recession has been felt in the Western Balkans, the extent of which will depend on the duration of the Covid-19 pandemic. This crisis represents an unprecedented shock that has surprised the world and its economy. People have moved to stay at home to slow and stop the spread of the virus and governments and societies face high human, social and economic costs.

"For the first time since the pandemic began, there is now hope for a brighter future. Progress with vaccines and treatment have lifted expectations and uncertainty has receded," OECD Chief Economist Laurence Boone said. Boone said - monetary and fiscal support must be funneled into stronger and better economic growth with investments in education, health, physical and digital infrastructure being a priority.

Discussion

Will globalization be reversed? Probably not, it is too important economic development for something like that to happen, but it could be slowed down. Do you, however, question whether you have learned lessons from this crisis? Will we learn to recognize, control, and regulate the risks that act as components of globalization? Because it seems that there is a great lack of cooperation and leadership that is necessary for that to happen.

The virus could have penetrated so deeply into the core of the world economy because it is a strongly connected system. And that, and not just a poor supply of masks and protective suits, proved to be a drawback in this pandemic. That is why the question is already hanging in the air, whether there will be some kind of "deglobalization" and stronger regionalization of production.

The corona reveals the dark sides of globalization. Interdependence, especially economic interdependence, will no longer be seen only as a source of security, but also as a source of insecurity. Thus, for example, we have come to the conclusion that we are completely dependent on medical products, which come from the other side of the globe, and that in times of crisis we cannot rely on them being able to reach us. At the same time, we discover that the virus, which appeared on the other side of the world, can change the life of each of us. These are the dark sides of globalization.

However, at the same time, we are experiencing the globalization of the spirit of each individual. Suddenly we started living in the same world. Imagine someone who does not speak any foreign language and who lives in a small town or village. This man can turn channels and listen to all languages, of which he does not understand a single word, but he knows exactly what the central news is about in each language. Because, the world only talks about one thing - Corona virus.

Conclusion

Overall, the economy appears to have recovered in 2022. Total economic output has more than recovered since 2020, when it hit its lowest level. The unemployment rate is again below 4%, as it was at the beginning of 2020, while the total employment is at the same level as it was before the start of the pandemic. However, seen from another angle, it seems that the economy will never be the same again, or will be in a post-Covid state for a long time. Just when it was thought that the crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic was behind us, the world was stunned by the news of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. The war in Ukraine additionally affected the global economic situation. According to the report Global Economic Perspectives, it is estimated that global growth will slow down from 5.7% in 2021 to 2.9% this year. Growth in emerging markets and developing economies is also expected to slow down from 6.6% in 2021 to 3.4% in 2022, which is significantly higher than the annual average of 4,8 in the period from 2011-2019. And in addition to the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, this is also due to the negative consequences of the war in Ukraine and the deterioration of the global environment. Growth forecasts in 2022 have been revised up by 70% in emerging markets and developing economies, including the vast majority of commodity-importing countries, as well as 4/5 of low-income countries. So, aside from the recession caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, this is the weakest year of growth for emerging markets and developing economies since 2009.

In addition to sharply declining global growth, there are other numerous risks that overlap and reinforce each other, primarily intensifying geopolitical tensions, growing financial instability and ongoing supply tensions. Continued geopolitical conflicts could further disrupt economic activity, create political uncertainty, and if they continue to intensify, could lead to the fragmentation of global trade, investment and financial systems. Inflation is higher than experts predicted, and has spread beyond food and energy drinks. The interruption of supply due to the Covid-19 crisis and war conflicts in the territory of Ukraine led to a jump in the price of energy and food. Record food prices have led to a global crisis that will push millions into extreme poverty, increasing hunger and malnutrition and thus threatening to wipe out hard-earned gains. The war in Ukraine, disruptions in the supply of goods and the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic are halting years of development and raising food prices to unprecedented levels. Rising food prices have a much greater impact on people in middle- and low-income countries, as they spend a larger proportion of their income on food than people in higher-income countries. This is supported by statistical data, so the agricultural price index as of July 15th, 2022 is 19% higher compared to January 2021. Corn and wheat prices are 15% and 24% higher compared to January 2021, while rice prices are lower by 11% (World Bank Commodities Price Data).

When it comes to domestic products, the situation is also alarming. The prices of domestic products are high in almost all countries. Data from February to June 2022 show a high inflation rate in almost all low- and middle-income countries: 94.1% of low-income countries, 88.9% of lower-middle-income countries and 87% of upper-middle-income countries had a level inflation above 5%, with many of them recording double-digit inflation. The share of countries with high income and high inflation also increased, with around 67.9% inflation when it comes to food prices (World Bank Commodities Price Data). According to the World Economic Bank's April 2022 Commodity Markets Forecast, the war in Ukraine has affected global patterns of commodity trade, production and consumption to the extent that it will maintain commodity prices at unprecedented levels until 2024 (World Bank Group, 2022 Commodity Markets Outlook, April 2022).

Even before the war, the price of food in Ukraine was high, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and geopolitical tensions additionally affect its growth. The goods most affected by the price jump are wheat, corn, edible oils and fertilizers. Global markets face potential risks through the following channels: dwindling grain supplies, higher energy prices, higher fertilizer prices and trade route disruptions due to major port closures. During the coming months, a major challenge will be access to fertilizers that can affect food production on many crops in different regions. As Russia and Belarus are the biggest exporters of fertilizers, this makes the situation even more complicated. Food shortages were warned by the heads of the World Bank Group, the International Monetary Fund, the United Nations Food Program and the World Trade Organization, who published a joint statement calling on the international community to take urgent action to address food insecurity, to keep trade open and thus, assistance was provided to vulnerable countries, including financing to ensure the most necessary needs (Joint Statement: The Heads of the World Bank Group, IMF, WFP and WTO call for urgent Coordinated Action on Food Security).

After the war in Ukraine, imposed policy trade increased. The global food crisis is growing in part due to the increasing number of food trade restrictions imposed by certain countries with the aim of increasing domestic supply and reducing prices. Thus, as of July 15th, 18 countries introduced 27 food import bans, while 7 countries applied 11 measures to limit exports (The World Bank, Food Security Update).

The data on the level of hunger in the world are alarming at the global level, so according to the report of the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) from 2022, the number of people affected by hunger increased in 2021 to 828 million, which is an increase of about 46 million compared to 2020, and 150 million more compared to 2019 (FAO: The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022).

Thus, a large increase in the hungry due to the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic is evident, however, after the war in Ukraine, the number of hungry has doubled compared to the situation after Covid-19. In addition, the World Food Program warns that the current food situation could worsen in 20 countries in the period from June to September 2022 (WFP: A Global Food Crisis). A rapid telephone survey conducted by the World Bank in 83 countries found that many people have gone without food or reduced their consumption during the Covid-19 pandemic. It is already known that reduced caloric intake and irregular eating can have numerous negative consequences for health and can leave lasting consequences on children's cognitive development.

The pandemic caused by the Covid-19 virus has also affected many other aspects, including tourism. Although experts predicted recovery by 2023, according to current forecasts, this is not yet possible. The delayed recovery was primarily influenced by the war situation in Ukraine. First of all, sanctions, high inflation and the loss of Russian and Ukrainian visitors are key factors in the further recovery of tourism. As stated in the report of the Economist Intelligence Unit, all of the above influenced their forecasts regarding the recovery of tourism in Europe to be pessimistic. According to the report, tourism in Europe was expected to return to the pre-pandemic level by 2023, however, the situation in Ukraine had a negative impact on tourism. As they point out, the war will affect the European tourism industry on four levels: the loss of Russian and Ukrainian tourists, airline and airspace restrictions, higher food and fuel costs, a major impact on passenger confidence and available funds (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2022: Tourism in 2022, Forecast).

The countries that will suffer the biggest blow in terms of tourism are Turkey and Poland, where, according to the predictions of the Economist Intelligence Unit, they will suffer the biggest drop in visitors in absolute terms, but Cyprus and Latvia will also feel the negative consequences, as they mainly relied on Russian tourists.

The war in Ukraine, although primarily a humanitarian disaster, delayed the recovery of tourism. This is supported by the fact that Russian tourists will be unwelcome in many destinations, as the report points out, but even so, they are limited in terms of travel, bearing in mind the bans of many airlines and restrictions on the use of air space. Meanwhile, millions of Ukrainians have been driven abroad by the war, but as refugees, not tourists. Across Europe, the war had the effect of raising commodity prices, which were already on the rise due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The prices of food and fuel are especially alarming, but the price increases of airline companies, which are already burdened with debt, are also significant. In addition, the prices of restaurants and hotels will significantly affect tourists, because the rise in prices of all goods will affect their disposable income, and in this sense, even if consumer confidence is restored, vacations are significantly more inaccessible to them.

The impact of war conflicts between Russia and Ukraine will not only affect the mentioned areas, but also on a global level. Before the pandemic disrupted global tourism flows, Russia was the world's 11th largest source of tourists, and Ukraine 13th. This is shown by data from the World Tourism Organization, which states that these two countries received 75 million tourists in 2019, which makes 5% of the total world number. Tourist spending was especially important, with Russians and Ukrainians contributing a total of US\$50 billion, which represents 8% of the world total, and Russia alone was the world's seventh largest spender. Now, however, the share of Russian and Ukrainian tourists will decrease, as the war and sanctions affect the travel routes and economies of these two countries. In absolute terms, Turkey was the most visited destination by tourists from Russia and Ukraine in 2018, attracting 6 million Russian and 1.4 million Ukrainian tourists, accounting for 16% of total arrivals to Turkey that year.

Several million Russians also go to Asian countries, such as Thailand and China, and neighboring countries such as Kazakhstan, which could be opened to them this year. However, two other popular destinations, Italy and Poland, will now be closed to them. On the other hand, some smaller destinations, with closer ties to Russia and Ukraine, will be hit even harder. Thus, in 2019, Russian tourists accounted for 20, 29 and 36% of tourists who visited Cyprus, Montenegro and Latvia (UNWTO, 2022: Impact of the Russian Offensive in Ukraine on International Tourism). Also, the loss of tourists will be felt in the destinations that attract the richest Russian and Ukrainian tourists, who usually spent a lot of money on restaurants, hotels and luxury stores. This applies to cities such as Milan, London and Paris, as well as popular cities such as Karlovy Vary in the Czech Republic and Baden in Germany.

The Covid-19 pandemic has also affected the education system around the world, leading to the partial or complete closure of schools, universities and other educational institutions. As of mid-April 2020, approximately 1.723 billion students were affected by school closures due to the Covid-19 pandemic. According to UNESCO research, over 160 countries have closed schools worldwide, representing 87% of the student population (UNESCO: COVID 19 Educational Disruption and Response, COVID 19: Educational Disruption and Response).

School closures have not only affected students and teachers and their families, but have far greater economic and social consequences. School closures due to the Covid-19 pandemic have highlighted many issues, such as: digital learning, poverty, food insecurity, homelessness, childcare, access to health insurance, digital tools and the internet, and so on. Families with a poor financial situation were particularly affected, leading to learning disabilities, irregular meals, childcare problems and constant exposure to economic costs due to parental unemployment. Namely, the inability to access technology and the Internet had the greatest impact on children from rural areas and vulnerable families. In addition to the lack of digital resources, students from large families were particularly exposed to problems, because they did not have a space to study at home. In response to the closure of schools, UNESCO recommended the use of distance learning programs and open educational applications, however, due to the aforementioned problems, many students were unable to follow the lessons in this way. A particularly sensitive issue is that some parents, who could not provide their children with the means to attend classes, exposed their children to work or forced them into early marriage in order to cope with the financial stress caused by the Covid-19 pandemic.

The consequences of the COVID-19 virus have affected millions of children to be exposed to hard labor. Factors that influenced it were poverty caused by the pandemic, due to the loss of jobs of parents or other family members, the death or illness of a guardian, and the like. The pandemic also affected many children taking care of the household and looking after their brothers and sisters, due to the closure of educational institutions.

According to a World Bank report, the number of people living in extreme poverty rose from 88 to 93 million in 2020. When a family faces financial losses, it usually puts pressure on the children as well, who are then exposed to hard work. According to studies by the International World Labor Organization and UNICEF, an increase of just 1% in poverty causes a 0.7% increase in child labor (ILO and UNICEF, Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act: Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act).

During the mass closure of schools, about a third of students did not have access to digital learning, due to the lack of access to the Internet, computers, phones and other means. During January 2021, around half of students still had a problem with a lack of access to digital learning. Denied access to schooling has led to child labor, as many families see it as a logical alternative. However, even when schools reopen, many children do not return to them. According to a report by the United Nations, about 24 million students have dropped out of school, and girls are particularly affected by this compared to boys, given that they are mainly responsible for household chores (ILO and UNICEF, Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act: Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act).

One of the key factors affecting children being exposed to work is the death, illness or disability of a parent. Many families were affected by death due to the consequences of the COVID-19 virus, and in that case, children had to worry about the finances of themselves or other family members. For example, in the United States of America, by February 2021, 43,000 children have lost at least one parent due to the COVID-19 virus. However, due to a number of factors, such as mortality and morbidity rates, family structure, and data

access, it is impossible to provide a global estimate based on US samples. However, these data indicate that the number of children who have lost a parent due to the COVID-19 virus could be in the hundreds of thousands. One of the problems that arose due to the COVID-19 virus is that child labor inspections have been reduced or even eliminated, due to precautionary measures, and without effective implementation of inspections, it is likely that the true number of children exposed to labor will remain undetected. In addition, there is also the problem that employers are likely to employ children who then pay less than adults, or delay and even withhold the payment of wages (ILO and UNICEF, Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act: Covid 19 and Child Labor: A Time of Crisis, A Time to Act).

One of the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic is nutrition, as many families rely on free or reduced-price school meals for their children. In the US, school meal programs are one way to fight hunger, so each school year more than 30 million children rely on schools that provide free or reduced meals, including breakfast, lunch, snacks and even dinner (The Counter: 30 million children rely on school lunch. Where do they eat when school's out? <https://thecounter.org/summer-hunger-new-york-city/>).

Although now the situation with the coronavirus has calmed down, and we are somewhat returning to normal, the fact is that it affected the education system and changed it. Although face-to-face and distant learning have their advantages and disadvantages, what is inevitable is that both teachers and students will have to get used to a new way of learning, since we can return to the online teaching model. Teachers, students and schools must follow new trends to prepare for future learning. While teachers will need to refine their methods to create the most engaging online environment for their students, students will need to take advantage of available technologies and learning resources. One of the positive things that happened after the Covid-19 pandemic is that we realized that learning can happen anywhere. And even before the pandemic, many places where learning was possible, such as museums, libraries, local events and lecture venues, began to digitize their processes and bring the learning experience to the online realm. Although it cannot be said that learning can happen anywhere these days, today we have many more online places where it can happen.

As many museums, libraries and the like have digitized their environments, all these possibilities should be used. Today, it is possible to virtually visit all those places with the help of the Internet. Although digital learning was a problem not only for students, but also for teachers, especially those of older generations, many states, supporting the Ministry of Education, offered free courses and workshops for this purpose. Although most states have returned to face-to-face learning, many schools are combining online learning with classroom learning. Thus, online teaching aids have become an indispensable tool for learning today, and their advantages are numerous.

Based on abovementioned, it can be said that the coronavirus has not only affected our lives, but, it seems, has fundamentally changed them. Although it affected numerous factors, primarily the economy, health, and many others, it seems that the society is slowly returning to normal, although it will take a long time. However, the bigger problem seems to be whether we have learned from it all.

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